

ENTERPRISE RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICE AND PERFORMANCE OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract: The study evaluated the enterprise resource management practice and performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to; examine the relationship between corporate performance and waste reduction, evaluate the relationship between customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The area of the study was the SMEs in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1232 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and ninety-three (293) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fifty-seven (233) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation(r) test statistic tool. The findings indicated Corporate performance had significant positive relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State $r(95, n=.233), .593 < .892, p>.05$). Customer service had significant positive relationship with output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $r(95, n=.233), .495 < .793, p>.05$). The study concluded that corporate performance and customer service had significant positive relationship with waste reduction and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others the management of food and beverage manufacturing firms should endeavour to maintain corporate performance to ensure that strategic priorities are executed and the key drivers of the business maintained to produce accurate and consistent financial information.

Keywords: Enterprise, Resource, Management, Practice, Performance, Food, Beverages, Manufacturing, firms.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

The use of enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems facilitates better business unit communication. This is a result of their comprehensive understanding of every facet of the company. However, because it involves issues with people and data, putting an enterprise resource planning system into place may be a difficult task. But with

the right preparation and communication, these difficulties may be solved (Prajapati, 2021). Implementing ERP is seen by many companies as a chance to examine and enhance key business procedures. When an organization's internal resources are integrated based on content, organizational capabilities are formed. The application of enterprise resource planning (ERP) in the realm of information technology can increase organizational capacities. ERP is a computer-based integrated system that is intended to manage business transactions and enable integrated planning, real-time production operations, and quick customer response, according to Aremu, Shahzad, and Hassan (2019). Material resource planning is one of the functions of an ERP system, which is an information system that unifies and automates all business departments finance, HR, logistics, etc. and aids in the overall management of all company resources that are integrated into a single system.

Systems for enterprise resource planning, or ERPs, are integrated solutions that handle the majority of an organization's operations and activities. According to Balic, Turulja, Kuloglija, and Pejic Bach (2022), enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems have emerged as the primary instrument for business integration and the realization of the "once only" principle in data entry. These developments lead to increased resource efficiency, the improvement of various organizational processes and capabilities, and ultimately, better business performance. ERP systems inside an organization require a sophisticated technological infrastructure and a high degree of coordination. ERP systems have long been in place in large companies around the globe, but small and medium-sized enterprises especially those in developing countries have not.

The capacity of a corporation to transform total manufacturing investment into production volume and tangible outcomes is the basis for measuring performance in manufacturing enterprises. According to Juma (2017), one of the most widely used company management systems is the enterprise resource planning (ERP) system, which offers businesses in large companies the advantages of seamless communication and real-time capabilities. But not every ERP deployment has been effective. There are several obstacles that businesses may face while deploying ERP systems as these systems impact people, processes, and corporations as a whole. The practice of assessing how effectively an ERP system satisfies the goals and expectations of its stakeholders is known as ERP performance measurement. Determining the link between ERP techniques and business performance is the primary goal of the research.

1.2 Statement of the problem

ERPs are a vital tool for any rapidly expanding company that wants to scale its operations, meet customer expectations, and optimize its processes. ERP boosts productivity across many departments by automating a range of company functions and procedures. Repetitive work is also lessened, freeing up time for other activities. ERP systems serve as a central repository for all facets of an organization's operations and are based on established business standards. ERP systems inside an organization require a sophisticated technological infrastructure and a high degree of coordination.

An organization may enhance team chemistry, expedite customer response times, decrease repetitive operations, and consolidate data by implementing an ERP system. ERP may greatly enhance supply chain operations in

companies by increasing their scalability, efficiency, and manageability. Unfortunately, due to subpar corporate performance and customer service inside the company, this goal is frequently not met.

Thus, it is important to address the ERP issues that are causing poor waste reduction and low production in order to both overcome this ERP obstacle and reap the advantages of applying ERP techniques in the firm. Therefore, the necessity to evaluate enterprise resource management practice and performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate enterprise resource management practice and performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the relationship between corporate performance and waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between corporate performance and waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Corporate performance has relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

1.6 Significance of the study

Enterprise resource planning (ERPs) are an essential tool for any fast-growing business that needs to optimize its systems, keep up with consumer demands, and scale its operations. With an ERP system, an organization can speed up customer response, eliminate repetitive tasks, consolidate data, and improve team dynamics and performance.

1.7 Scope of the study

The study was based on enterprise resource planning practices and performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The key management issues in the study were corporate performance, customer service, waste reduction and output. The geographical scope of the study was Enugu State, one of the five states that made up the South Eastern Nigeria. The time scope of the study was 2021-2024.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual review

2.1.1 Enterprise

An enterprise is a business endeavor started by an entrepreneur, who also takes on the risks, organization, and administration of the firm. An enterprise is any organizational unit, organization, or group of organizations that work together to serve clients with certain goods or services and have a shared set of objectives. Accordingly, the term "enterprise" refers to a variety of organizational forms, independent of their size, ownership structure, style of operation, or geographic location (Giachett, 2010). Regardless of whether or not profit realization is the primary goal, a commercial enterprise is defined as an ongoing organization of autonomous economic activity. An enterprise is a unit of an organization that produces products or services and has some autonomy in making decisions. An enterprise may operate in many locations and engage in multiple economic activities. One or more legal units can make up a business (Eurostat, 2019).

2.1.2 Resource

Anything that is useful and enriches your life is a resource. A "Resource" is everything that is found in nature that is useful to humans, including air, water, food, plants, animals, minerals, metals, and other materials (Toppr, 2023). Certain resources found in nature have a lot of promise, but we lack the knowledge and technology to fully use it. These continue to exist in nature as stock resources as a result. The availability of natural resources is a prerequisite for all resources created by humans. Anything that is useful and enriches your life is a resource. Everything that is found in nature that is useful to humans, including air, water, food, plants, animals, minerals, and metals, is referred to as a "Resource." Each such resource has a value that is determined by its utility as well as other elements. Land, capital, material, machinery, time, energy, labor, management, knowledge, competence, and information are all crucial components of a business (Safeopedia, 2023).

2.1.3 Planning

Thinking through the steps necessary to accomplish a goal is the process of planning. It is predicated on foresight, the essential ability to journey across time in the mind. The core managerial role is planning, which entails determining in advance what needs to be done, when it needs to be done, how it needs to be done, and by whom. It is an intellectual process that establishes the goals of an organization and creates several strategies for achieving those goals (Business, 2023). Additionally, planning is the predetermination of goals and actions to be performed in order to accomplish specified goals successfully and efficiently (Sujan, 2023). It's an intellectual process that involves determining ahead of time what has to be done, how to do it, when to do it, and who should do it.

2.1.4 Enterprise resource planning practices

The integrated administration of key business operations, frequently in real time and facilitated by software and technology, is known as enterprise resource planning, or ERP. A sort of software called enterprise resource

planning (ERP) assists businesses in automating and managing essential company operations for peak productivity. ERP software streamlines operations throughout the organization by coordinating data flow between business activities inside an organization and delivering a single source of truth (Microsoft, 2023). The project team's caliber and expertise have a significant impact on the achievement of ERP implementation success. Over the past few decades, enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems have emerged as a vital tool for companies. An ERP system functions as a common database for all operational and financial data from throughout the organization and automates crucial business operations (Ian, 2022). According to the findings, an organization should think about the following practices before implementing ERP successfully: creating a plan with specific goals and objectives, getting internal support and commitment, choosing the appropriate software, allotting enough resources, providing training, and handling change (Mutuku, 2020).

2.1.5 Components of enterprise resource planning practices

2.1.5.1 Corporate performance

A collection of all the techniques and procedures used to promote success inside a company is called corporate performance management (sometimes referred to as business performance management, enterprise performance management, or even enterprise and corporate performance management). Corporate intelligence encompasses corporate performance management. It revolves around the organization's strategy and is solely focused on the accomplishments and shortcomings of the organization. Corporate performance is a composite measure of an organization's effectiveness in achieving its objectives. Although they mostly depend on the firm, these objectives often fit into the predetermined categories of shareholder, market, and financial success (Ansarada, 2023). All businesses need to have an organizational plan, especially during difficult times. It guarantees that the fundamental business drives are upheld and that strategic goals are carried out. Stated differently, the corporate performance of that organization is overseen.

2.1.5.2 Customer service

The direct, one-on-one conversation that takes place between a customer and a representative of the business providing the product is known as customer service. It is the support and guidance a business offers customers who purchase or utilize its goods or services. Although the standards for customer service vary by business, boosting profits is ultimately considered a well-performed service (Lucas, 2015). A variety of consumer services are referred to as customer support, and its purpose is to help consumers utilize products correctly and economically. It comprises support for product planning, setup, instruction, troubleshooting, upkeep, upgrading, and disposal. These services could even be rendered at the location where the client uses the item or service. It is necessary to carry out service innovation and assess value propositions from the standpoint of the value created by and experienced by the client. Although it has always been a vital component of company, customer service is today more crucial than ever. Consumers have high expectations of brands. Every stage of the customer experience, from the first contact to the after-purchase period and beyond, must involve ensuring their pleasure (Savage, 2023).

2.1.6 Performance

According to McNamara (2018), performance is defined as the accomplishment of a duty in a way that absolves the performer of all contractual obligations. The comparison of an organization's actual performance in three different areas financial performance, market performance, and shareholder value with its goals and objectives is known as organizational performance. Ability factors, motivation factors, individual competencies, management support, organizational support, self-efficacy, empowerment factors, and coaching can all have an impact on performance (Maharani & Widiyanto, 2017). Performance standards are the goals or objectives that need to be met in order for a firm to operate. The goal of performance management is to guarantee that teams and individuals receive the tools necessary for growth, the acknowledgement they merit for motivation, and the accountability to understand expectations. According to Carpi, Douglas, and Gascon (2017), performance management makes sure that teams agree on what matters most and that the organization's principles are upheld in real life.

2.1.7 Components of performance used in the study

2.1.7.1 Waste Reduction

Anything that lowers waste by initially utilizing less material is considered waste reduction. The method of preventing waste by reducing or eliminating the amount of resources initially utilized is known as waste reduction or source reduction. After trash reduction, reuse is the second-best waste management strategy. Reusing a substance in its existing form repeatedly is known as reuse. Reusing something means preserving part or all of the resources and energy used to create it (Clinton, 2023). Compared to recycling, waste reduction is more comprehensive as it includes strategies for keeping items from becoming waste before they are recycled. Reusing items like dishrags in place of paper towels, buying more sturdy goods, and reusing materials like plastic and glass containers are all examples of waste reduction strategies. Due to the numerous negative effects improper waste management may have on society's environment, economy, and social structure, waste management is a crucial topic that has received a lot of attention on a global scale (Ugwu, Ozoegwu, Ozor & Agwu, 2021). Waste is an ineffective byproduct of human activity that physically includes the same materials as those found in products that are valuable. Individuals, companies, organizations, towns, government agencies, and institutions like hospitals or schools may all minimize waste.

2.1.7.2 Output

The term "output" refers to a nation's gross domestic product, which is the total amount of goods and services produced over a specific time period. The phrase can be used to describe all labor, energy, products, or services generated by a machine, factory, or individual (Market Business News, 2022). In business organizations, output refers to the total amount of products or services generated inside the organization. If a company produces a single item, its output may be defined as the quantity of that commodity produced in a certain time frame, such a month or a year. The revenues from product sales, after accounting for price adjustments, might also be used to estimate

the production of the firm. The total productivity metric defines inputs and outputs as their respective economic values. The revenue produced during a manufacturing process is calculated as the value of outputs less the value of inputs. It is a gauge of a manufacturing process' overall effectiveness and, as such, the goal that must be attained (Yadav and Marwah, 2015).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The study was anchored on resource-based view theory

2.2 Resource based view theory (RBV)

Resource based view theory (RBV) was established by Penrose (1959) and Wernerfelt (1984) as a collection of resources and capabilities that when combined, develop competences Resource based theory which holds that business enterprises must have required resources at their disposal so as to gain advantage competitively and enhance organizational performance (Wernerfelt, 1984). According to resource-based theory, an organization's resources, such as knowledge, might occasionally be insufficient or limited when employed as inputs in its operations. According to Raduan, Jegak, Haslinda, and Alimin (2009), the resource-based theory generally maintains that businesses should take advantage of and optimize the variations in their resource endowments, skills, and competences as a foundation for developing strategies to get a competitive edge in the marketplace. As a result, businesses ought to be able to successfully manage any given knowledge in order to achieve organizational success. Business enterprise can improve on their performance if they have the appropriate resources (that is knowledge) which are well managed with the right tools. In other words, organizations can attain performance through effective and efficient management of knowledge as organizational resource using appropriate tools. The study hinges on the Resource Based View (RBV) Theory which holds that organization are rent seeking units that develops and deploy resources (assets and capabilities) to realize competitive advantage. The theory examines in great depth why organizations succeed or fail in their respective fields of endeavor. The organization's internal resources are analyzed and interpreted, with a focus on utilizing resources and capabilities to develop plans that achieve long-term competitive advantages and enhance organizational performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

Kalu, (2016), conducted a study on Corporate Governance and Profitability of Listed Food and Beverages Firms in Nigeria. At its core, the goal of a firm is to create sustainable profitability. Moreover, corporate governance needs to endeavor to guarantee this consistent upswing in organizational performance. Various scientific domains have given understanding the effect of corporate governance on business profitability more attention throughout time. The purpose of this study was to investigate the connection between corporate governance and business profitability using data from eight food and beverage companies that were listed between 2004 and 2014 on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. In a panel data context, the data were analyzed using multiple regression utilizing Ordinary Least Squares along with basic descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings showed a positive correlation between board size and net assets per share and return on equity at the five percent significance level. On the other hand, there is a positive correlation between board composition and net assets per share, but a

negative correlation with return on equity. The results of board gender diversity showed a favorable association between return on equity and net assets per share, but board skills and competence showed a negative relationship with these metrics. Even given the contradictory findings, one may argue that the empirical data provide credence to the idea that corporate governance and business profitability are positively correlated.

Ndubuisi-Okolo, Anekwe, Nwanonigwe, and Chukwuemeka, (2020), conducted a study on Effect of Strategic Orientation on Performance of Food and Beverage Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The impact of strategic orientation on food and beverage companies in Enugu State was the main subject of this study. It specifically examined how market orientation affected the market share of food and beverage companies in the state of Enugu. The study used a structured questionnaire that was set up to capture the study's unique purpose, hence a survey research methodology was used. Two hundred (200) people in all were taken out of the registered food and beverage companies in Enugu State. Using a census sampling method allowed for the inclusion of all participants. A systematic questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect the data from the respondents. Simple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypothesis once the data were created and descriptively assessed. The outcome showed that, in Enugu State, market orientation significantly increased the market share of food and beverage companies. According to the report, food and beverage businesses in Enugu State should thus be vigilant and attentive to environmental changes that might negatively impact their operations. This plan would assist in reducing the concerning rate of failures plaguing Nigeria's and Enugu State's industrial industries.

Ugwu, Okonkwo, and Orga, (2022), conducted a study on Operational Risk Management Practices and Performance of Aluminum Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. The performance and operational risk management procedures of aluminum manufacturing companies in the state of Enugu were assessed in the study. The specific goals were to investigate the following relationships: risk avoidance strategy and profitability; response planning and waste reduction; and risk transfer to a third party and customer retention in Enugu State's aluminum manufacturing companies. Simple random sampling and the survey technique were employed in the study. The questionnaire's administration served as the main source of data. The research population comprises the proprietors and employees of the chosen business owners in Enugu city, with a total population of 2,407,47. Using the Cochran (1963) sampling approach, the sample size of 331 was calculated with a 5 percent margin of error. A total of 287 employees responded the completed questionnaire with accuracy. Using the Sprint Likert Scale, the data were presented and evaluated by mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses were analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

Ede, Okolie, and Igwe, (2023), established a study on Organizational Structure and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (Smes) in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study evaluated organizational structure and performance of small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to; examine the relationship between skill variety and reduced expenses and evaluate the relationship between delegation and units of output produced by SMEs in Enugu state. The total population for the study was three thousand, one hundred and ninety-four (3194). The sample size of three hundred and forty-two (342) was drawn using Freund

and William's formula at 5 percent error margin. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire and interviews. A total of three hundred and forty-two (342) copies of questionnaire were distributed while two hundred and seventy-eight (278) copies of questionnaire were returned. Pearson correlation coefficient(r), was used to test the hypotheses, the findings include that there was positive significant relationship between skill variety and reduced expenses of SMEs in Enugu state, $r(95, n=278) = .519 < .790, p < .05$. There was positive significant relationship between delegation and units of output produced by SMEs in Enugu state, $r(95, n=278) = .494 < .760, p < .05$. The study concluded that skill variety and delegation had positive significant relationship with reduced expenses and units of output produced by SMEs in Enugu state. Asogwa, Nwoha, Nwankwo, (2023), conducted a study on Effect of Firm Productivity on Financial Performance of Foods and Beverages Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. From 2011 to 2020, the study looked into how company productivity affected the financial performance of Nigerian companies that manufacture food and beverages. The study's particular goals are to determine how Nigerian food and beverage manufacturing companies' return on assets is impacted by sales growth, sales per employee, and profit per employee. Out of the fifteen (15) food and beverage manufacturing companies that were listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange at that time, a sample of eight (8) enterprises was chosen. T-statistics and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data gathered from the chosen businesses. The study's findings demonstrated that all three independent variables—sales growth, sales per employee, and profit per employee—had a positive and statistically significant impact on the returns on assets of the companies that produce food and beverages. These results suggest that the return on assets of the companies rises in tandem with improvements in sales growth, profit per employee, and sales per employee.

Agbionu, Ikon, and Agbodike, (2017), conducted a study on Effective Competency Modeling and The Performance of Food and Beverage Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria: A Triangulated Critical Analysis and Associational Evaluation. The prevalence of subpar performance in Nigerian private sector organizations has increased to the point that stakeholders feel burdened and uneasy about the situation in the companies where their capital is invested. The study looked at how much effective competence management is used by Enugu State's food and beverage firms before hiring new employees. The main goal is to determine whether there is any connection, if any, between worker performance in food and beverage firms in Enugu State, Nigeria, and competent management. A comprehensive, critical, and evaluative review of the literature was conducted before an efficient competency framework model was created. Using a structured questionnaire, data was collected from primary sources and analyzed using percentages. The SPSS Statistical Package version 20 was used to test hypotheses using the chi-square statistical technique. The study's sub variables had positive and statistically significant correlations, as demonstrated by the results and findings. Recommendations were made in light of the conclusion, which was reached in light of the results.

Agbaeze, Nnabuko, Ifediora, and Ekoja, (2017), conducted a study on Comparative Analysis of Consumers' Patronage of Beverage Food Drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The general goal of this study, "Comparative Analysis of Consumers' Patronage of Beverage Food Drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria," was to identify which

beverage food drink brand is most popular in the state. The specific goals were to identify the factors influencing consumer purchasing behavior, assess the health benefits of consumers' choices, assess the impact of promotions on consumer purchasing decisions, and ascertain the degree to which product taste influences customer satisfaction and repeat purchase for Cadbury Bournvita and Nestle Milo. The survey research design was used in the study. Out of an unlimited number of customers in Enugu State, 384 consumers of Cadbury Bournvita and Nestle Milo were randomly selected using the Cochran sampling procedure. The data was collected using a standardized questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale, and analysis was conducted using a 5% or 0.05 confidence level. The results showed that a variety of factors, including product availability, packaging, quality, brand loyalty, and advertising, had an impact on consumer spending.

Nwulu, and Nwokah, (2018), conducted a study on Customer Service Management and Marketing Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. This study looks at the connection between the marketing effectiveness of Nigerian companies that produce food and beverages and customer service management. The cross-sectional survey design is used, and the data comes from fifteen (15) of the nation's major manufacturing companies. Relationships are evaluated using null hypothetical statements that use Spearman's rank order correlation to analyze the insignificance of the impact of customer service management on three metrics of marketing performance: profitability, market share, and sales growth. Based on the data demonstrating substantial correlations between the variables, all hypotheses were disproved. According to the study's findings, customer service management considerably improves marketing performance, which in turn improves metrics like sales growth, market share, and profitability for food and beverage companies operating in Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

Ugwu, Ebeke, and Igah, (2021), conducted a study on Effect of Human Sustainability on the Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. The study assessed how human sustainability affected the productivity of Enugu state's industrial companies. The precise goals were to: assess the impact of health investments on the caliber of services provided by the chosen food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing companies in Enugu State; investigate the impact of education investments on the financial success of the same chosen companies. The survey technique was employed in the investigation. Personal interviews and questionnaire administration served as the main sources of information. Using the Freund and William formula, a sample size of 352 employees from the population of 4250 was chosen. 322 employees properly completed the questionnaire and returned it. This resulted with a response rate of 91%. Content analysis was used to assess the validity of the instrument, and the results were positive. Regression was used to assess the hypotheses. The results showed that investments in health had a positive impact on the level of service provided by the chosen food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing companies in Enugu state ($F(95, n = 322) = 230.956, p > 0.05$), and investments in education had an impact on the companies' profitability ($F(95, n = 322) = 646.267, p > 0.05$). The study found that the quality of service and profitability of the chosen food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing companies in Enugu state were positively impacted by investments in health and education.

Bartoo, Namusonge, and Makokha. (2023), established a study on Moderating effect of organization culture on the relationship between supplier development and organizational performance in food and beverage manufacturing companies in Kenya. A more effective strategy that businesses may use to enhance and maintain their organizational performance would be supplier development. Finding out how organization culture influences the link between supplier development and organizational performance in Kenyan food and beverage manufacturing enterprises was the aim of this study. The resource dependency hypothesis was applied in a descriptive survey research design for the study. Procurement managers and officials from 217 food and beverage manufacturing enterprises in Kenya that were registered with the Kenya Association of Manufacturers as of 2017 comprised the target demographic. There were 248 responders in the sample. By use of a questionnaire, primary data were obtained. To evaluate the reliability coefficient, Cronbach's alpha was employed. The researcher used expert judgment to establish the instrument's content validity. With the use of SPSS V26, descriptive and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. Regression results ($\beta = 0.058$, $t = 4.68$, $P < 0.05$) indicated a significant interaction between supplier development and organization culture on the performance of food manufacturing enterprises. The performance of Kenyan companies that manufacture food and beverages and supplier development are influenced by organizational culture. The study concluded that supplier development affects how well manufacturers of food and drink perform.

3.0 Methodology

The area of the study comprised of four (4) selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The choice of these firms was due to high number of staffs, Capital base above 15 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1232 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and ninety-three (293) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fifty-seven (233) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 80 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.812 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation(r) test statistic tool.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data presentation and Analyses

4.1.1 The relationship between corporate performance and waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 4.1.1: Responses on the relationship between corporate performance and waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	∑FX	- X	SD	Decision
1 Ensuring that strategic priorities are executed minimized expenses in the organisation.	395 79 33.9	148 37 15.9	207 69 29.6	54 27 11.6	51 21 9.0	855 233 100%	3.54	1.306	Agree
2 Maintaining the key drivers of the business promotes productivity.	530 106 45.5	148 37 15.9	132 44 18.9	81 27 11.6	38 19 8.2	929 233 100%	3.79	1.343	Agree
3 The monitoring of the financial health of the firm in real time increases opportunity for success.	440 88 37.8	148 37 15.9	180 60 25.8	28 24 10.3	24 24 10.3	820 233 100%	3.61	1.351	Agree
4 Employee participation in the decision making in the matters that concerns them facilitates better business decisions.	495 99 42.5	224 56 24.0	114 38 16.3	51 17 7.3	23 23 9.9	907 233 100%	3.82	1.320	Agree
5 Corporate performance enables long- term planning.	600 120 51.5	236 59 25.3	66 22 9.4	36 18 7.7	28 14 6.0	966 233 100%	4.09	1.208	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.77	1.3056	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1, 116 respondents out of 233 representing 49.8 percent agreed that ensuring that strategic priorities are executed minimized expenses in the organisation with mean score 3.54 and standard deviation of 1.3.6. Maintaining the key drivers of the business promotes productivity 143 respondents representing 61.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.79 and standard deviation of 1.343. The monitoring of the financial health of the firm in real time increases opportunity for success 125 respondents representing 53.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.61 and standard deviation of 1.351. Employee participation in the decision making in the matters that concerns them facilitate better business decisions 155 respondents representing 66.5 percent agreed with mean

score of 3.82 and 1.320. Corporate performance enables long- term planning 179 respondents representing 76.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.09 and standard deviation 1.208.

4.2. The relationship between customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 4.2.1: Responses on the relationship between customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Quality customer service retains customers and extracts more value from them.	475	288	54	66	15	898	3.58	1.271	Agree
		95	72	18	33	15	233			
		40.8	30.9	7.7	14.2	6.4	100%			
2	Implementing vital customer service improves relationship with customers and the business.	510	312	57	16	26	921	3.95	1.291	Agree
		102	78	19	8	26	233			
		43.8	33.5	8.2	3.4	11.2	100%			
3	Top-notch customer service help firms recoup customer acquisition costs.	625	264	54	12	18	973	4.18	1.178	Agree
		125	66	18	6	18	233			
		53.6	28.3	7.7	2.6	7.7	100%			
4	The long- term customer relationship increase profits of the organisation, and their productivity.	555	385	39	36	14	1029	4.09	1.175	Agree
		111	77	13	18	14	233			
		47.6	33.0	5.6	7.7	6.0	100%			
5	Good customer service allows the organisation to remain competitive in the marketplace.	410	368	39	58	17	92	3.83	1.241	Agree
		82	92	13	29	17	233			
		35.2	39.5	5.6	12.4	7.3	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.926	1.2312	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.1, 167 respondents out of 233 representing 71.7 percent agreed that Quality customer service retains customers and extracts more value from them with mean score 3.58 and standard deviation of 1.271. Implementing vital customer service improves relationship with customers and the business 180 respondents representing 77.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.95 and standard deviation of 1.291. Top-notch customer service help firms recoup customer acquisition costs 191 respondents representing 81.9 percent agreed with mean score of 4.18 and standard deviation of 1.178. The long- term customer relationship increase profits of the organisation, and their productivity 188 respondents representing 80.6 percent agreed with mean score of 4.09 and 1.175. Good customer service allows the organisation to remain competitive in the marketplace 174 respondents representing 74.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation 1.241.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Test of hypotheses one: Corporate performance has relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Table 4.3.1.1 shows the Pearson correlations on corporate performance has relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Correlations

	Ensuring that strategic priorities are executed minimized expenses in the organisation.	Maintaining the key drivers of the business promotes productivity.	The monitoring of the financial health of the firm in real time increases opportunity for success.	Employee participation in the decision making in the matters that concerns them facilitates better business decisions.	Corporate performance enables long-term planning.
Ensuring that strategic priorities are executed minimized expenses in the organisation.	1	.790** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233	.888** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233	.637** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233	.593** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233
Maintaining the key drivers of the business promotes productivity.	.790**	1	.892** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233	.810** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233	.790** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233
The monitoring of the financial health of the firm in real time increases opportunity for success.	.888**	.892**	1	.774** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233	.705** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233
Employee participation in the decision making in the matters that concerns them facilitates better business decisions.	.637**	.810**	.774**	1	.669** Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 233
Corporate performance enables long-term planning.	.593**	.790**	.705**	.669**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.1.1 showed the pearson correlation matrix on corporate performance and **waste reduction** showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .593 < .892. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that corporate performance had significant positive relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State (r = .593 < .892). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .000 with at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r =.593 < .892, p <.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .593 < .892$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that corporate performance had significant positive relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r=.360 < .972, p<.05$).

4.3.2 Test of hypotheses two: Customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 4.3.2.1 shows the Pearson correlations on customer service and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Correlations

	Quality customer service retains customers and extracts more value from them.	Implementing vital customer service improves relationship with customers and the business.	Top-notch customer service helps firms recoup customer acquisition costs.	The long- term customer relationship increase profits of the organisation, and their productivity.	Good customer service allows the organisation to remain competitive in the marketplace.
Quality customer service retains customers and extracts more value from them. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 233	.589** .000 233	.495** .000 233	.672** .000 233	.684** .000 233
Implementing vital customer service improves relationship with customers and the business. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.589** .000 233	1 .000 233	.663** .000 233	.793** .000 233	.638** .000 233
Top-notch customer service help firms recoup customer acquisition costs. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.495** .000 233	.663** .000 233	1 .000 233	.715** .000 233	.519** .000 233
The long- term customer relationship increase profits of the organisation, and their productivity. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.672** .000 233	.793** .000 233	.715** .000 233	1 .000 233	.678** .000 233
Good customer service allows the organisation to remain competitive in the marketplace. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.684** .000 233	.638** .000 233	.519** .000 233	.678** .000 233	1 .000 233

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.2.1 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on customer service and output showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.495 < .793$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed) and implies that customer service had significant positive relationship with output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State ($r = .495 < .793$). The computed correlation coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with an alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .495 < .793$, $p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .495 < .793$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that customer service had significant positive relationship with output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .495 < .793$, $p < .05$).

5.1 Summaries of findings

The results of the study revealed that

- i. Corporate performance had significant positive relationship with waste reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State ($r(95, n=.233), .593 < .892, p > .05$).
- ii. Customer service had significant positive relationship with output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State, ($r(95, n=.233), .495 < .793, p > .05$).

5.2 Conclusions

The study concluded that corporate performance and customer service had significant positive relationship with waste reduction and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. ERPs are an essential tool for any fast-growing business that needs to optimize its systems, keep up with consumer demands, and scale its operations. ERP facilitates effective maintenance by centralizing scheduling, ticketing and work order management, while also enabling powerful data tracking and analytics to improve maintenance effectiveness.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the study

- i. The management of food and beverage manufacturing firms should endeavour to maintain corporate performance to ensure that strategic priorities are executed and the key drivers of the business maintained to produce accurate and consistent financial information.
- ii. For effective customer service there is need for direct connection between customers and the organisation as improved relationships with customers increases business profits.

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